

Automated Dating of Medieval Manuscripts with a New Dataset

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Abstract. Automated manuscript dating is a long-awaited valuable tool for scholars in their research of historical documents. This study presents a new dataset of medieval Hebrew manuscripts annotated with dates. Our initial experiments focus on documents written in the Ashkenazi square script, allowing us to refine our methodologies in a manageable setting before addressing more complex script types. Also, to accurately reflect the script’s historical evolution, we adopt a novel classification approach for time periods of varying lengths, which acknowledges the uneven development of the script over time. We perform extensive experimentation with a variety of deep-learning models and show that the regression approach is more appropriate for estimating the date of the manuscript compared to categorical classification.

Keywords: Historical document images · Automated dating · Historical dataset · Regression · Classification

1 Introduction

Automated manuscript dating holds potential applications across various domains. It is a valuable tool for aiding scholars in analyzing undated or debated works. Additionally, the integration of automatic manuscript dating can help researchers in historical linguistics, archeology, sociology, and also enhance the relevance of results in the field of information retrieval.

In conventional manuscript analysis, manual processing is the primary method of analysis, which requires researchers to possess specialized expertise in paleography, a field that focuses on studying historical writing systems. However,

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the growing digitization of historical documents over the last few decades necessitated the development of computational techniques to process and analyze digital collections. Automated dating methods can contribute to streamlining and improving the accuracy of dating processes, making scholarly research and information retrieval more efficient and effective.

Several studies have explored the task of automatic dating of historical manuscripts [46,38,18,52,31,32,44], including dedicated competitions [8,7,37]. However, the majority of the studies focused on Latin scripts. There are still a number of languages with significantly different writing characteristics that remain understudied. Particularly, to the best of our knowledge, no studies systematically explored automated dating of historical documents in Hebrew.

Our key contributions include:

- We present a new dataset of medieval documents annotated with date. In this study, we focus on manuscripts written in the Ashkenazi square script. Starting with this well-defined subset enables us to develop and refine our methodologies in a controlled, manageable environment before we expand our analysis to the lesser studied script types.
- To more accurately and logically reflect the script’s evolution, we propose a classification of time periods that vary in length. This approach recognizes the unequal rates of change and development that the script underwent at different historical stages.
- We conducted extensive experiments using a variety of models and compared regression versus categorical classification approaches. We argue that the regression approach is better suited for the date estimation task. We also evaluated and compared the page-level and manuscript-level scenarios. Our experiments lay the groundwork for future research.

We believe that this research contributes not only to the field of medieval Hebrew manuscripts studies but also has broader implications for advancing automated date estimation techniques in manuscript analysis.

2 Related Work

Driven by the need to assist scholars and reduce manual effort, various methods for automated dating of historical manuscripts have been developed over the last decades. These methods range from statistical models to deep neural networks.

Earlier works leveraged traditional machine learning methods, including statistical models [17,42,46], Random Forests [39,41], SVM [5], SVR [6], and Self-Organizing Maps [19,20].

In recent years, deep learning-based approaches have gained prominence in almost all fields, including automated document analysis. Li *et al.* [23] proposed a CNN-based approach in enhancing OCR accuracy by leveraging estimated publication dates. Wahlberg *et al.* [47] focused on Swedish historical manuscripts, using a CNN-based GoogleNet architecture for feature extraction and SVR for dating, and showed the potential of CNNs to learn features for accurate manuscript

dating. Sidorov [38] explored paleographic dating of Birch Bark Manuscripts, employing an elastic model of grapheme deformation and features learned by CNNs. Studer *et al.* [40] investigated the impact of ImageNet pre-training on historical document analysis tasks. The research assessed pre-training effects on character recognition, style classification, manuscript dating, semantic segmentation, and content-based retrieval, providing insights into the benefits of pre-training in diverse tasks. Hamid *et al.* [18] utilized CNNs for automatic feature learning from small patches. The study explored writing styles' matching as a basis for estimating the date of manuscript origin. Yu and Huangfu [52] employed a Long-Short Term Memory Network (LSTM) to capture non-linear relationships within character sequences for automated dating of ancient Chinese texts. Series of the ICFHR and ICDAR competition [8,7,37] provided a comprehensive overview of historical document classification tasks, including font group/script type, location, and date estimation. The competitions showed varying difficulty levels of these classification tasks. Adam *et al.* [1] introduced a hierarchical fusion of traditional and ResNet-extracted features for dating historical manuscripts in Arabic. Molina *et al.* [28] proposed a system for historical document retrieval for date estimation of document collections, using a ranking loss function, smooth-nDCG, to train a CNN for document ordination. Assael *et al.* [2] presented "Ithaca" – a deep neural network designed to restore, attribute, and date ancient Greek inscriptions. The papers of Paparrigopoulou *et al.* [31,32,33] addressed automated dating of Greek papyri images with several classifiers, both traditional machine learning (SVM, decision trees, Random Forests) and deep-learning (DenseNet, VGG, EfficientNet, ResNet). Pavlopoulos *et al.* [34] trained several regression models to predict dates for Greek papyri and leverage a Convolutional Neural Network to provide precise date estimations for papyri with disputed or vaguely defined dates [35]. Tvalavadze *et al.* [44] utilized the CNN for automated dating of the works of Georgian poet Galaktion Tabidze.

Several studies have explored the automated analysis of Hebrew manuscripts. The early work of Wolf *et al.* [48] experimented with the script style classification on the Cairo Genizah collection. Prebor *et al.* [36] introduced a methodology to predict migration patterns and locations by combining script type with temporal data. The works of Vasyutinsky Shapira *et al.* [45] and Droby *et al.* [10,13] investigated the use of deep-learning models for classifying medieval Hebrew scripts using the VML-HP dataset. Feigenbaum-Golovin *et al.* [16] explored computational paleography for ancient Hebrew inscriptions and analyzed processing methods, including binarization, letter segmentation, automatic handwriting analysis, and writer identification. Droby *et al.* [12] compared hard and soft-labeling approaches for script classification. Naamneh *et al.* [29] focused on Aramaic incantation bowls, introducing a new dataset and proposing a Multi-Level-of-Detail architecture for improved accuracy of script similarity analysis.

3 Dataset Overview

Sfardata is the name of a database created by the Hebrew Paleography Project, under the direction of Malachi Beit-Arié, of blessed memory. The Hebrew Palaeography Project was established in 1965 with the goal of inventorying and studying all medieval Hebrew codices prior to 1540 which contain an explicit mention of their date or can be precisely dated. Consequently, the manuscripts were located in more than 250 public and private collections around the world, and their codicological and paleographical features were described. Eventually, the project described more than 3,300 manuscripts within the time span from the 9th century to 1540; some contain the mention of the place of copying.

In the early 1970s Malachi Beit-Arié initiated a pioneering effort to convert the documented data into a computerized form. Numerous changes were introduced following the development of computer technologies, and eventually, in the early 2010s, SfarData was converted to an online database. Today, it is hosted by the National Library of Israel.

Paleographically, manuscripts in the Sfardata are described according to their script mode (square, cursive, semi-cursive) and to their geographical type. The six geographical types are Oriental (Egypt, Palestine, Syria and Lebanon, Iraq, Iran, Uzbekistan and Bukhara, Eastern Turkey); Sephardic (the Iberian Peninsula, Provence and Languedoc, North Africa, and Sicily); Italian; Ashkenazi (France and England, the Holy Roman Empire, Central, and Eastern Europe), Byzantine (Greece, the Balkans, Western Asia Minor, and regions surrounding the Black Sea); and Yemenite.

Each manuscript is illustrated by two or more photographs. One of the photographs is often the page with the colophon (the scribe’s note indicating the name of the scribe, the date, and often the place of copying). The colophon is often scribed in a different script type mode than the main text.

The compiled dataset contains 299 accurately labeled page images excerpted from 166 different manuscripts written in Ashkenazi square script. The manuscripts are dated from 1176 to 1533, and their distribution over the years is presented in Appendix, Figure 4. In this study, we focused our initial experiments exclusively on documents written in the Ashkenazi square script. This decision was made for several reasons. Firstly, there is a unique evolution of each Hebrew script type across different periods, which precludes a standardized period classification applicable to all types. Consequently, it is essential to define classifications individually for each script type. Secondly, the Ashkenazi script, along with Sephardic and Italian scripts, are relatively well-studied [4,14,15,30]. Square scripts are more uniform than semi-cursive and cursive script modes, and dating the later requires profound paleographical training. Providing automatic solutions for this problem is both challenging and rewarding. Finally, by beginning with a smaller, well-defined subset—such as the Ashkenazi square script—we can develop and refine our methodologies in a controlled, manageable context before extending our analysis to more varied and lesser studied script types. For the Ashkenazi square script, our team’s paleographer proposed a classification into four classes, as listed in Table 1. This classification does not

Table 1. Classes for Ashkenazi square manuscripts dating

Class	Years Interval	Number of Manuscripts	Number of Pages
1	1176 – 1250	9	20
2	1250 – 1306	39	66
3	1306 – 1400	54	96
4	1400 – 1533	64	117

adhere to equal-length time periods; rather, it is logically structured to reflect the evolution of this script.

4 Models Overview

In this section, we provide an overview of the diverse range of models employed in our experiments, each showcasing unique advancements and adaptations to address specific challenges in computer vision tasks.

We begin with the Vision Transformer (ViT) [9], an architecture that directly applies transformer principles to sequences of image patches, outperforming traditional convolutional networks while requiring fewer computational resources. ViT’s success has spurred the development of several derivative models, each aiming to enhance performance and efficiency in image classification tasks.

Data-Efficient Image Transformers (DeIT) [43] introduce resource-efficient image classification models, leveraging a teacher-student training strategy to achieve competitive accuracy with reduced data and computing resources. Similarly, BERT Pre-Training of Image Transformers (BEiT) [3] integrates masked image modeling inspired by BERT, surpassing supervised pre-training methods and excelling in downstream tasks like image classification and semantic segmentation.

Document Image Transformer (DiT) [22] extends the self-supervised learning objective of BEiT to document images, achieving state-of-the-art results in document image classification and analysis tasks, addressing the scarcity of labeled document data.

The Swin Transformer [25] introduces a hierarchical architecture with shifted windows for efficient self-attention computation, achieving impressive performance across various tasks with linear computational complexity relative to image size. Swin Transformer V2 [24] further improves training stability and resolution adaptability, setting new benchmarks in large-scale model performance.

ConvNeXT [49,26] modernizes ResNets with vision Transformer design principles, demonstrating remarkable performance in image classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation tasks.

Convolutional Vision Transformer (CvT) [50] integrates convolutions into the ViT architecture, enhancing performance and efficiency, particularly on ImageNet-1k tasks, while MobileViT [27] combines lightweight CNNs with ViTs’ global processing capabilities, achieving superior performance suitable for mobile devices.

FocalNet [51] introduces a novel focal modulation mechanism, replacing self-attention in vision transformers, and achieving superior performance across various tasks with comparable computational costs.

Each of these models represents a unique approach to leveraging transformer architectures in computer vision, showcasing advancements in performance, efficiency, and adaptability to address the evolving challenges in image processing tasks.

5 Experiments

We compare the results of the regression and classification approaches. Our hypothesis focuses on how different training-test split strategies impact model performance, particularly in the context of data regression and data classification tasks. We aim to determine whether the "Page-Level Split" or the "Manuscript-Level Split" yields superior results. This hypothesis suggests that the way we divide the dataset for training and testing can significantly influence model performance, especially in tasks involving predicting dates. By examining data regression and data classification problems, we seek to understand the effects of splitting strategies on model performance across these specific tasks.

5.1 Dataset Preparation Schemes

The dataset comprises 299 pages from 166 manuscripts spanning 1176 to 1533, each associated with a specific year.

Our data preparation strategy involves two primary splitting strategies: page-level split and manuscript-level split. The page-level split randomly divides the document pages into training and testing sets. This methodology promotes model generalization across individual pages by incorporating variability across manuscripts. Specifically, pages from the same manuscript are distributed across both training and testing sets, allowing the model to learn from a diverse range of page layouts, contents, and styles. This split method is common in tasks where pages from the same manuscript can be treated as independent samples.

The manuscript-level split allocates pages associated with manuscripts originating from the same years to either the training or testing set exclusively. This ensures that the model's ability to generalize to entirely new manuscripts is rigorously tested. By mimicking real-life scenarios where models predict the labels of manuscripts they have not encountered during training, this approach evaluates the model's robustness and adaptability to unseen data.

We adhere to a standard split of 70% for training and 30% for testing datasets (split at page and manuscript levels). Within the training phase, a validation dataset is derived from the 20% of the training data. Our model training and testing procedures involve the extraction of patches from document images, following the patch generation method detailed in [11]. These patches are uniformly extracted based on text scale, with an average of 5 lines per patch as shown in Appendix, Figure 5.

For the manuscript-level split, 6700 patches are extracted for training and 930 test set. For the page-level split, we include 9800 patches for the training set and 2160 for testing. Both regression and classification strategies maintain this split, ensuring equitable comparisons across tasks.

5.2 Models Preparation

As was mentioned in Section 4, the experimented were conducted with a variety of architectures of Vision Transformers, encompassing a diverse array of models such as Vision Transformer (ViT) [9], ConvNeXt [49,26], DeiT [43], FocalNet [51], Convolutional vision Transformers (CvT) [50], Shifted Window Transformer (Swin) [25], SwinV2 [24], MobileViT [27], BERT for Image Transformers (BEiT) [3], and Document Image Transformer (DiT) [22]. We also explored various versions of these models, including base, small, and tiny variants, as shown in Tables 2 and 3. The primary distinction among these versions lies in the size and complexity of the models, as well as the number of parameters they contain.

To adapt these models for regression tasks, we utilized a straightforward modification by removing the last layer of the classifier and appending a tensor with dimensions of 1×1 . This configuration enabled the model to predict the year as a continuous variable. For classification tasks, we modified the models by truncating the last layer and replacing it with an output layer comprising four classes corresponding to specific intervals. This transformation allowed the models to categorize the manuscripts into distinct temporal periods. By implementing these adjustments, we tailored the architectures to suit the respective regression and classification objectives.

5.3 Regression Study

For the regression task, we constructed models according to the methodologies outlined in Section 5.2. To ensure consistency across all models, we employed the Adam optimizer [21] throughout the training process. Each model was initialized from scratch and trained for a duration of 20 epochs, with a fixed batch size of 8. The learning rate was set to 0.002 for all models to facilitate stable and efficient training. During the training process, input images were partitioned into patches of size 256×256 , allowing the models to capture detailed spatial information. Mean Squared Error (MSE) was utilized as the primary loss function to quantify the discrepancy between predicted and ground truth year values. This choice of loss function is well-suited for regression tasks, enabling the models to minimize the deviation from the true year values during training. Through this standardized training protocol, we aimed to ensure uniformity in training procedures across all models and a fair comparison of their performance in regression tasks.

We utilized the MSE metric to calculate the error rate (ER). This metric measures the average error between the predicted and ground truth year values across the test set. Tables 2 and 3 list the ER values from the experiments over the test set. Both tables present the performance of regression models with

Table 2. Performance of Regression Models with Page-Level Split

Model	ER	ER with 5% Trim	ER with 10% Trim	Median ER
BEiT _{base}	25.45	19.23	15.10	5.0
ConvNeXt _{base}	25.14	18.69	14.69	5.0
ConvNeXt _{tiny}	26.35	21.17	17.37	12.0
CvT ₁₃	28.97	23.90	19.68	13.0
CvT ₂₁	28.80	23.76	20.39	16.0
DeiT _{base}	25.44	19.26	15.01	4.0
DeiT _{small}	27.94	21.22	16.85	6.0
DeiT _{tiny}	29.74	23.71	19.17	8.0
DiT _{base}	45.31	40.35	36.49	37.0
FocalNet _{base}	25.47	18.61	14.21	3.0
FocalNet_{small}	21.87	16.04	11.95	4.0
FocalNet _{tiny}	26.18	19.30	15.03	4.0
MobileViT _{base}	31.87	27.88	24.64	23.0
MobileViT _{small}	45.76	40.62	37.23	44.0
MobileViT _{tiny}	53.82	49.28	45.50	50.0
Swin _{base}	27.32	21.44	17.01	6.0
Swin _{small}	27.34	20.21	15.52	6.0
Swin _{tiny}	31.02	24.09	19.77	11.0
Swinv2 _{base}	25.29	18.88	14.33	3.0
Swinv2 _{tiny}	25.13	18.45	14.30	5.0
ViT _{base}	27.18	20.33	15.97	4.0

Table 3. Performance of Regression Models with Manuscript-Level Split

Model	ER	ER with 5% Trim	ER with 10% Trim	Median ER
BEiT _{base}	61.99	55.97	51.51	53.0
ConvNeXt _{base}	56.25	51.79	48.15	50.0
ConvNeXt _{tiny}	57.35	52.88	48.97	48.0
CvT ₁₃	55.27	50.73	46.96	47.5
CvT₂₁	52.87	48.27	44.43	40.5
DeiT _{base}	56.90	52.10	48.16	47.0
DeiT _{small}	53.55	48.50	44.56	44.0
DeiT _{tiny}	61.54	56.35	52.14	53.5
DiT _{base}	64.19	59.46	55.47	56.0
FocalNet _{base}	62.53	56.10	52.05	54.0
FocalNet _{small}	62.15	57.08	53.00	54.0
FocalNet _{tiny}	61.30	56.45	52.32	54.0
MobileViT _{base}	54.16	49.65	45.78	47.0
MobileViT _{small}	53.99	49.27	45.20	44.0
MobileViT _{tiny}	53.31	47.74	43.85	43.0
Swin _{base}	59.57	54.28	49.57	43.5
Swin _{small}	58.25	53.74	50.06	46.0
Swin _{tiny}	62.01	56.15	51.21	50.0
Swinv2 _{base}	59.80	54.26	49.76	48.0
Swinv2 _{tiny}	55.29	50.72	46.75	44.0
ViT _{base}	58.20	53.32	49.07	50.0

two different data preparation strategies: page-level split and manuscript-level split. For the page-level split (Table 2), FocalNet_{small} achieved the top results, with the lowest ER of 21.87. MobileViT_{tiny} exhibits the highest error rate of 53.82, indicating its relatively poor performance compared to other models in this approach. On the other hand, when considering the manuscript-level split, CvT₂₁ achieved the best results with the lowest error rate of 52.87.

Though the page-level split showed much lower error rates, the model might not truly learn to generalize across different manuscripts. It might learn specific features of the manuscript because its pages appear in both sets. In order to ascertain which approach, either the page-level split or manuscript split, is more effective, we have devised a rigorous evaluation plan. Firstly, we constructed a "blind dataset" that includes 5 pages from the manuscripts that were not used in our dataset, with each page contributing 30 patches, a total of 150 patches. None of these patches have been previously employed in either of the splitting schemes, i.e., the samples used for this evaluation are entirely separated from those utilized in constructing the training/test splits.

Figures 1.a and 1.b illustrate the disparity between the performance of each model on the test set from the split (depicted by blue columns) and the blind test (highlighted by the green column) for page-level and manuscript-level approach. Based on the analysis of Figure 1, it becomes evident that the page-level approach exhibits considerable weakness, with an average difference of 50.45 between the performance on the test set and the blind test. The page-level approach falls significantly in real-life scenarios. On the other hand, the manuscript-level split approach showcases a lower average difference in performance among models, averaging 10.9. This highlights the contrast between the manuscript-level approach and the page-level approach, emphasizing the effectiveness of the former in achieving more controlled and stable results in real-life scenarios. Therefore, we conclude that the manuscript-level split approach is preferable to applications where the model needs to work with previously unseen documents.

The analysis of Figure 1.b provides insightful observations regarding the performance of different models in the context of the manuscript-level approach. Notably, models encompassed by dotted red rectangles achieve a remarkable feat, exhibiting less than a 5-year difference between their performance on the test set and the blind test. This observation underscores their robustness in constructing stable and reliable features, indicative of their capability to adapt effectively to unseen data scenarios. Other models, not surrounded by the highlighted rectangles, display a disparity of more than 5 years between their performance on the test set and the blind test.

Our investigation into the impact of extreme differences (outliers) on manuscript-level split regression models' performance highlights the sensitivity of MSE to values with significant deviations from the norm. These outliers can substantially distort MSE assessments, falsely indicating poorer model performance even when models perform adequately on most of the data. To address this, we analyzed the differences between mean and median error values for various models on both test and blind test datasets as shown in Appendix, Table 6 and Figure 6.

The average difference between the mean and median values on the test dataset is approximately 8.73, while for the blind test dataset, it is significantly higher at approximately 17.56. This indicates a higher presence of outliers in the blind test dataset, leading to larger discrepancies between mean and median errors. Consequently, while evaluating model performance, it is crucial to consider both mean and median values, particularly in the presence of outliers, to avoid misleading assessments based on MSE alone.

Most of the models have a lower median (black line) than mean (red dotted line), such as CvT₂₁, BEiT_{base} as shown in Appendix, Figure 6. This leads to a significant difference between the mean and median errors, indicating the presence of a few high-error instances of outliers that skew the mean.

To mitigate the potential impact of outliers that could skew the evaluation results, we utilized a trimmed mean approach and median criterion. Specifically, we applied trimming parameters of 5% and 10% to data points that exhibit extreme deviations from the dataset’s tails. By employing this trimmed mean methodology, we aimed to obtain a more robust and reliable estimation of the model’s performance, which is less susceptible to the influence of anomalous data points. This comprehensive evaluation framework allowed us to assess the regression models’ performance accurately and objectively, providing insights into their efficacy in predicting manuscript pages years with minimal bias and distortion from outliers.

5.4 Classification Study

The classification task was carried out as follows. We followed the methodologies outlined in Section 5.2. The Adam optimizer [21] was utilized throughout the training process. Each model underwent initialization from scratch and was trained for 10 epochs, with a constant batch size of 8. A learning rate of 0.002 was chosen for all models. Similarly to the regression experiments, throughout the training phase, input images were segmented into patches of dimensions 256×256 . Cross Entropy Loss was adopted as the primary loss function to assess the disparity between predicted and ground truth class labels. This choice of loss function is particularly well-suited for classification tasks, facilitating the minimization of the difference between predicted and actual class distributions during training.

Utilizing the same dataset, we can directly compare the performance of models trained under different splitting strategies, aiming to identify the optimal approach for our classification task. For the evaluation, we utilized Precision and Recall metrics. The classification results are presented in Table 4 and Table 5.

Based on Table 4, the model with the best precision is Swinv2*tiny*, with a precision of 84.19%, and the model with the best recall is also Swinv2*tiny*, with a recall of 84.49%. Therefore, Swinv2*tiny* achieves the highest precision and recall among the models listed in the table. In Table 5, among the models listed in the table, ViT_{base} has the highest precision (66.51%), indicating its ability to correctly identify positive instances. However, Swinv2*tiny* has the highest recall (62.82%).

(a) Models error rate comparison over the test and blind test using page split scheme

(b) Models error rate comparison over the test and blind test using manuscript split scheme

Fig. 1. Errors rate comparison over different models

(a) Precision Page-Level

(b) Recall Page-Level

Fig. 2. Precision and Recall values for different models, page-level split

Table 4. Performance of Classification Models with Page-Level Split

Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
BEiT _{base}	77.91	77.71	FocalNet _{small}	81.34	80.51
ConvNeXt _{base}	83.27	81.68	FocalNet _{tiny}	81.94	80.35
ConvNeXt _{tiny}	81.95	74.59	MobileViT _{base}	76.76	73.95
CvT ₁₃	84.13	76.36	MobileViT _{small}	81.64	77.53
CvT₂₁	83.73	81.13	MobileViT _{tiny}	76.31	74.55
DeiT _{base}	82.89	79.38	Swin _{base}	82.28	73.81
DeiT _{small}	81.38	79.02	Swin _{small}	80.74	73.44
DeiT _{tiny}	80.68	74.13	Swin _{tiny}	81.06	73.69
DiT _{base}	79.57	74.49	Swinv2 _{base}	81.97	83.42
FocalNet _{base}	80.60	77.70	Swinv2 _{tiny}	84.19	84.49
ViT _{base}	78.54	76.51			

Table 5. Performance of Classification Models with Manuscript-Level Split

Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
BEiT _{base}	59.98	54.32	FocalNet _{small}	57.68	53.25
ConvNeXt _{base}	63.69	57.98	FocalNet _{tiny}	54.58	55.40
ConvNeXt _{tiny}	62.56	54.00	MobileViT _{base}	55.37	57.76
CvT ₁₃	55.31	50.24	MobileViT _{small}	54.62	56.47
CvT₂₁	64.62	60.45	MobileViT _{tiny}	51.12	49.81
DeiT _{base}	52.31	53.20	Swin _{base}	61.72	59.81
DeiT _{small}	52.78	44.83	Swin _{small}	65.17	59.16
DeiT _{tiny}	56.53	52.75	Swin _{tiny}	61.57	55.61
DiT _{base}	55.86	51.38	Swinv2 _{base}	63.74	62.17
FocalNet _{base}	54.87	50.89	Swinv2 _{tiny}	62.46	62.82
ViT _{base}	66.51	56.90			

As in the regression task, we use a 'blind test' set to compare different dataset-split approaches. Figures 2.a and 2.b depict the disparity between precision and recall of each model on the test set (represented by green columns) and the blind test scores (blue columns) for the page-level approach. Upon analyzing Figure 2, it becomes evident that the page-level approach exhibits significant weaknesses, particularly in effectively addressing the blind test data. With an average difference of 43.39% and 37.44% for precision and recall, respectively, between the performance on the test set and the blind test, the page-level approach falls short in real-life scenarios. Nevertheless, specific models, such as DeiT_{base} and BEiT_{base}—highlighted by dotted red rectangles in Figure 2.a—demonstrate exceptional performance, achieving precision differences of less than 10 between their performance on the test set and the blind test. This observation underscores their robustness in constructing stable and reliable features, indicative of their ability to adapt effectively to unseen data scenarios. Similarly, Figure 2.b showcases models like DeiT_{base}—also encompassed by dotted red rectangles—achieving recall differences of less than 10% between their performance

on the test set and the blind test. Overall, while models trained on a page-level approach exhibit adaptation with blind datasets, DeIT_{base} stands out as an exception, achieving consistently good and closely aligned results in the blind dataset.

Figures 3.a and 3.b reveal a low disparity between precision and recall in model performance across both the test set and blind test data, with a difference of only 10% between their performance on the test set and the blind test. These models are highlighted by dotted red rectangles, emphasizing their notable consistency. The minimal differences observed in both precision and recall averages, with values of 9.14% and 10.70%, respectively, suggest a promising level of consistency in model performance across both the test set and blind test data. This indicates that, on average, the models maintain stable and reliable performance when confronted with previously unseen data scenarios. Such minimal disparities indicate that the models effectively generalize their learned patterns to new instances, showcasing a robust ability to adapt to novel data environments.

In conclusion, while both approaches have their merits, the manuscript-level approach outperforms the page-level approach in terms of stability and adaptability, making it the preferred choice for real-world applications requiring robust performance across diverse scenarios.

6 Conclusions

In this study, we have introduced a new dataset of medieval Hebrew manuscripts. Our initial experiments focused on manuscripts written in the Ashkenazi square script. We implemented a classification system for time periods that vary in length to reflect the nuanced evolution of the script over different historical stages. We compared the regression and classification approaches with various deep-learning models for the date estimation task. We also compared and analyzed different dataset split approaches. We argue in favor of manuscript-level split. In addition, our findings confirm that regression approaches are superior for the task of date estimation when compared to categorical classifications. Currently, we are extending our dataset to include additional script styles and modes to perform future experiments on a more diverse set of manuscripts.

Fig. 3. Precision and Recall values for different models, manuscript-level split

A Appendix

Fig. 4. Distribution of manuscripts/pages over the years

Fig. 5. Examples of the extracted patches. The patches are extracted with an average of 5 lines per patch.

Fig. 6. The difference between the mean and median values on the blind test for each model

Table 6. Mean and Median Errors for Test and Blind Test Sets

Model	Test		Blind Test	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median
BEiT _{base}	61.99	53	58.29	33
ConvNeXt _{base}	56.25	50	62.77	49
ConvNeXt _{tiny}	57.35	48	70.02	65
CvT ₁₃	55.27	47.5	74.34	79
CvT ₂₁	52.87	40.5	51.8	26
DeiT _{base}	56.90	47	55.79	37.5
DeiT _{small}	53.55	44	53.29	35
DeiT _{tiny}	61.54	53.5	63.37	42
DiT _{base}	64.19	56	82.05	99
FocalNet _{base}	62.53	54	54.81	35
FocalNet _{small}	62.15	54	81.76	36
FocalNet _{tiny}	61.30	54	75.21	30
MobileViT _{base}	54.16	47	75.41	101.5
MobileViT _{small}	53.99	44	87.51	91
MobileViT _{tiny}	53.31	43	85.23	105
Swin _{base}	59.57	43.5	86.85	71
Swin _{small}	58.25	46	81.85	81
Swin _{tiny}	62.01	50	80.57	75
Swinv2 _{base}	59.80	48	68.71	44
Swinv2 _{tiny}	55.29	44	65.47	49
ViT _{base}	58.21	50	57.06	39

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